

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF QUANSER DC SERVOMOTOR SYSTEM USING LINEAR REGRESSION MACHINE LEARNING MODEL

Rishi PL, Iswarya M, K Kalaiselvi,

Rishi PL: Department of ECE, SNS College of Technology, Coimbatore, India

Iswarya M: Department of ECE, SNS College of Technology, Coimbatore, India

K.Kalaiselvi: Department of ECE, SNS College of Technology, Coimbatore, India

First Author E-Mail ID : rishiteta@gmail.com

Second Author E-Mail ID : iswaryamanishankar@gmail.com

Third Author E-Mail ID : deanece@snsct.org

Abstract

The D.C servo motor is a stable system. In a real-time, stable system is easy to control and it fits for any controllers. This D.C servo motor is used for aircraft rudder position control. The D.C servo motor consists of a weight disk that mounted on the rotor. If there is a change in the weight of the disk produces an error value. Here the method of machine learning algorithmic procedure is implemented to reduce the error of desired characteristic if speed and applied voltage.

Introduction

The D.C servo motor is a stable system. In a real-time, stable system it is easy to control and it fits any controller. The D.C servo motor consists of a weight disk that mounted on the rotor. Quanser was founded in 1989 responding to the need for desktop hardware platforms optimized for teaching and research in engineering education. Quanser is the global standard in engineering lab equipment for teaching and research, specializing in Controls, Robotics, and Mechatronics. Implementation of quanser DC servo model and analysing its performance using machine learning algorithm. Design of transfer function model state space analysis and design of algorithmic procedure to reduce the error of desired speed and applied voltage.

System description and modelling

The Quanser QUBE-Servo 2 D.C motor is a direct rotary servo system. The servo motor shaft is connected to the load hub disk. The hub is a metal disk used to mount the disk or rotary pendulum and has a moment of inertia of J_h . A disk load is connected to the output shaft with a moment of inertia of J_d . The back-emf voltage $e_b(t)$ depends on the speed of the motor shaft ω_m

and the back-emf constant of the motor K_m . To find the speed of the motor no need to add an integrator and to find the position of the motor adding the integrator is an essential part. In this model the integrator is added to find the position of the Quanser QUBE-Servo DC motor. D.C motor is helpful to control the yaw position of the motor. D.C Qube servo motor is a stable system. State space model which represents the system parameter of the motor.

Figure 1: Quanser Qube Dc Servomotor

Stability of the DC servo motor system

The D.C servo motor is stable or marginally stable system $2 \ 0.0000 + 0.0000i, -5.7067 + 9.1123i, -5.7067 -9.1123i$ values obtained from state space model. This value is helpful for Poles and Zero plot. This implies the system inherently is stable and thus needs a proper controller to be designed.

Physical Parameter of the DC servo motor system

The physical parameters of DC servo motor system and its various parameter specifications are listed below like terminal resistance, torque constant, motor back emf constant, etc..This essential parameter shows the absolute design parameter used to control the motor model. The table of physical parameter model are represented below

Table 1 : Dc Servo Motor Parameter

Symbol	Description	Value
DC Motor		
R_m	Terminal resistance	8.4Ω
k_t	Torque constant	0.042 N.m/A
k_m	Motor back-emf constant	0.042 V/(rad/s)
J_m	Rotor inertia	4.0 × 10⁻⁶ kg.m²
L_m	Rotor inductance	1.16 mH
m_h	Load hub mass	0.0106 kg
r_h	Load hub radius	0.0111 m
J_h	Load hub inertia	0.6 × 10⁻⁶ kg.m²
Load Disk		
m_d	Mass of disk load	0.053 kg
r_d	Radius of disk load	0.0248 m

Quanser Qube DC Servo motor circuit

The quanser qube dc servo motor system motor and load are specified are below circuit diagram with applied voltage and lumped circuit element

Figure 2: QUBE-Servo 2 DC motor and load

Motor Model and Motor block representation with speed and torque

Figure 3: Motor model

Figure 4: Motor block representation with speed and torque

Closed loop reference speed vs Output speed

Motor block diagram and its specifications are processed in Matlab the input command speed and output speed are taken. The figure given below the input reference speed and output speed are shown below.

Figure 5: Closed loop reference speed vs Output speed

Machine learning algorithm- linear regression

It is a supervised Machine learning algorithm used to predict the output value with the given input. Regression analysis is a statistical method used in the problems of optimization or minimising. Error of the model by using least mean square error method or for the process of control Purposes. Here we have taken the linear regression method to observe the linear relationship between applied DC voltage and speed of the motor performance in a linear progression to reduce the error and to make them linear use the concept of mean square error method which is taking the difference between average of squared values of estimated value and actual value.

Linear regression is a method of modelling the target value based on independent predictors mainly used for forecasting for finding the relationship between two independent and dependent variables. To find the relationship between dependent and independent variables and to draw a best fit line using linear equation is called LinearRegression. Motive of the algorithm is to find the best values for slope and intercept and drawing the best fit line.

Linear regression is generally classified into two types simple linear regression and multiple linear regression Here we used simple linear regression it is a supervised machine learning algorithm used to predict the output value with the given input. Regression analysis is a statistical method used in problems of optimization or minimising.

Error of the model by using least mean square error method or for the process of control Purposes. Here we have taken the linear regression method to observe the linear relationship between applied DC voltage and speed of the motor performance in a linear progression to reduce the error and to make them linear use the concept of mean square error method which is taking the difference between average of squared values of estimated value and actual value. Datasets are collected in torque vs current and it's plot is represented below

Figure 6: Plot of torque vs current

The above figure 6 the torque vs current dataset plot has been specified. The linear regression coefficient algorithms are executed and loops of regression coefficients are observed using python programming packages. The linear regression slope value and intercept values are derived. The following plot image figure 7 shows the regression coefficient value.

Figure 7: Regression coefficient loop of slope and intercept

The errors of the model are reduced using cost function. It helps us to find the best values for slope and intercept that will provide the best fit line. Cost Function is also known as mean square error method. We can minimize the error between predicted and actual value by using the below formula.

The regression plot is derived successfully and plotted given below figure. Linear regression machine learning model is an algorithmic procedure plotted using the python package. The figure 8 represented below the linear regression plot.

Figure 8: Linear Regression machine learning plot current vs torque plot

Conclusions

Typically traditional controllers like Proportional Derivative (PD), Proportional Integrator (PI), Proportional Integrator Derivative (PID) are implemented. Here the method of machine learning algorithmic procedure is implemented to reduce the error of desired characteristic if speed and applied voltage. Desired machine learning model will be used in this method to observe the quanser dc servo motor system.

Acknowledgments

Shyamsundar PL and K Kalaiselvi provided guidance and help during the research and preparation of the manuscript.

References

- [1] A. V. Oppenheim, *Signals and Systems*. Old Tappan, NJ: Prentice Hall, 1982.
- [2] N. S. Nise, *Control Systems Engineering*, 7th ed. Nashville, TN: John Wiley & Sons, 2013.
- [3] B. C. Kuo, *Automatic Control Systems*, 7th ed. Philadelphia, PA: Prentice Hall, 1995.
- [4] P. L. Shyamsundar, P. L. Rishi, and P. L. Jamuna, "LQR based Fuzzy Logic Rudder Control System using DC Servo Motor," in 2019 5th International Conference on Advanced Computing & Communication Systems (ICACCS), 2019, pp. 124–127.
- [5] G. Farahani and K. Rahmani, "Speed control of a separately excited DC motor using new proposed fuzzy neural algorithm based on FOPID controller," *J. Control Autom. Electr. Syst.*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 728–740, 2019.
- [6] H. D. Taghirad and P. R. Belanger, "An experimental study on modelling and identification of harmonic drive systems," in *Proceedings of 35th IEEE Conference on Decision and Control*, 2002, vol. 4, pp. 4725–4730 vol.4.